

LEXICO SEMANTIC NATURE OF OF PHRASEOLOGISMS IN THE STORIES OF ABDULLA QAHHOR

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***Abstract:** The particular features of nations and the characteristics of individual human consciousness can both be reflected in phraseological units. The development of linguistic units that are distinctive in non-cognate languages is influenced by the unique consciousness of humans as well as by individual and national factors. In this article, the linguistic and cultural characteristics of phraseology are highlighted through the example of texts specific to the belles-lettres style. Literary examples are used to analyze lexical-semantic issues in expressions.*

***Key words:** Phraseological units, lexical-semantic, emotion and feelings, expression, culture, mentality, stories, nation.*

The phraseological fund of the language is the source of knowledge about the culture and mentality of people. Phraseological units contain the information about the peoples' ideas, life, habits, rituals, moral, behavior, culture, history, peoples' entity and consciousness [7:116]. Research of the phraseological systems and their comparison and contrast gives us the possibility to find out and define logical or associating thoughts of different people and their general and distinctive features. **og'zi qulog'iga yetmoq:** ma'nosi: xursand bo'lmoq. *Walking on air* Kechqurun og'zim qulog'imga yetkudek bo'lib bir do'ppi yong'oq ko'tarib keldim (O'.Hoshimov Dunyoning ishlari).

olamdan o'tmoq: varianti:olamdan ketdi. Ma'nosi: o'lmoq. *Down in the dumps* Meni shuncha o'limdan asrab qolgan odam shundoq ko'z o'ngimda olamdan o'tdi (O'.Hoshimov Ikki eshik orasi)

Abdullah Kahhar is known as a master of stories. in his stories, we see a lot of phraseological combinations. Examples of folk wisdom in the works of A. Kahkhor in a number of cases form the basis for the success of the story. Below, we will consider the linguistic and semantic meanings specific to the Uzbek people through their use in the stories of Abdulla Qahhor. Uyda tovush chiqarmaslik uchun Marg'uba tishini tishiga qo'ygan sayin Javlon haddidan oshaverdi ("Muhabbat"), for example. So in the sentence, we can see a **tishini tishiga qo'ymoq** expression suitable for putting up with. We can also see lingvocultural features in the sentences with the following phraseology:

Palata eshigi oldida bizni hindiga o'xshagan qop-qora, katta-katta ko'zlari yonib turgan bir yigit, aftidan, Masturaning eri kamoli ehtirom bilan kutib oldi va har qaysimizga ayrim minnatdorchilik bildirib, ichkariga yo'lladi. (Abdulla Qahhor Ming bir jon) By means of the phrase, the writer expressed the meaning of joy and cheerfulness in this sentence.

— *Ajab qildim, — dedi Turobjon titrab, — jigarlaring ezilib ketsin! Bu so'z unga qanday ta'sir qilganini faqat boshqorong'i xotingina biladi. Turobjon bu gapni aytdi-yu, xotining ahvolini ko'rib achchig'idan tushdi, agar izzat-nafs qo'ysa hozir borib uning boshini silar va: «Qo'y, xafa bo'lma, jahl ustida aytdim», der edi.* In this sentence you may see a lot of phrasemas used its secondary meanings. **jigarlaring ezilib ketsin** In the play, the wife of Turobjon says these words because she is sad that she is hungry for pomegranates but cannot bring them. It is said with the purpose of saying that I have done well now; don't be sad. Next expression *achchig'idan tushdi*, stopped getting angry and calmed down. So last one express feeling of angry, native speakers says *up in arms* in this occasion.

Turobjon do'ppisini boshidan oldi va qoqmoqchi bo'lganida ko'zi yirtiq yengiga tushdi, yuragi achidi: endi uch-to'rt suv yuvilgan yangigina yaktak edi! This phrase is

used in the sense of pity. By this, the writer emphasizes that the product was still a new thing.

Turobjonning ko'ziga negadir oqsoq mushuk ko'rindi. Mushuk yirtilgan yengini esiga tushirdi, avzoyi buzildi. You are upset about something and no longer have the patience to deal with it if you are at your wit's end. *Uning avzoyidan «esiz jo'xori, qatiq, o'tin» degan ma'noni anglab xotin, ko'ngli tortmasligiga qaramasdan, kosani bo'shatdi, ammo darhol tom orqasiga o'tib ko'zlari qizargan, chakka tomirlari chiqqan holda qaytdi.* 1 / 3 Abdulla Qahhor. Anor (hikoya)

— *Kishining yuragini qon qilib yuborasan, — dedi anchadan keyin. — Nainki men asal olsam! Asal otliqqa yo'q, hali biz piyoda-ku! Xo'jayinga bir oshnasi sovg'a qilib kelgan ekan, bildirmasdan... o'zidan so'rab oz-rog'ini oldim.* If we pay attention to this given example, the writer expresses the meaning of (tortured) by making the heart

— *Adabiyot muallimi oshnangizdir.*

— *Be, Saltikov bilan kim dedingiz hali, Shchedrinmi? Shuni bilmasa men qulog'ini tagi bilan sug'urib olaman. Qutbiddinov hamon kular edi.* You feel really irritated if you go off the deep end. This statement can also be used to indicate that someone has taken something to its final extreme and has begun to act unreasonably. English speakers uses to lose your temper, to be on edge, to break your heart, to get cold feet in the position by means of degree.

— *Ikkita anor uchun xotiniigizni serpul odamga oshirgani uyaling! Bu gap Turobjonning hamiyatiga tegdi. «Jigarlaring ezilib ketsin» degani xotiniga qancha alam qilgan bo'lsa, bu gap Turobjonga shuncha alam qildi.* Abdulla Qahhor. Anor (hikoya) The expression "pained" corresponds to the definitions of "suffered", "sorrowed", "sad". The word "Alam qilmoq" means to be upset, to be offended, to be depressed. The writer is conveying the meaning of the phrase in plain and simple language.

Agar Muhayyo Anvarga ko'ngil qo'ysa, boshini osmonga yetkazgan bo'ladi. In this sentence, we can see two expressions, of course, the use of this expression depends on

the artistic skill of the writer. Abdulla expressed the word (to love) through the phrase "ko'ngil qo'ymoq" and described it with the idiom mentality of the Uzbek people. Now let's pay attention to the next used expression: the meaning of on the top of the world, over the moon (happy) in a simple way, and the meaning is clearly revealed in the reader's mind.

Muborakxonim birpas dami ichiga tushib ketdi-yu, Hakimjonga yopishdi ("Muhabbat" hikoyasidan). In this sentence, the expression "dami ichiga tushmoq" artistically expresses the meaning of "to be afraid", shaking like a leaf or blood runs cold.

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